

1 Evidence that MX1 and MX2 possess actual functions as reporters of interferon signaling.

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7 MX1 and MX2 have anti-viral restriction factor like qualities that are a part of interferon immune defense
8 and their activation is utilized by some as a surrogate of interferon system activity. We present here
9 quantitative evidence that indicates the genes, when expressed as transcripts, are kept at a similar
10 message number, a number that is relatively low and that likely does not change between cell to cell in a
11 group of cells of the same type, or in a tissue when examining the same cell type. Increases in MX1 and
12 MX2 message quantity may then possess an alarm or reporter type quality, alerting cooperating systems
13 that antiviral-type activity is occurring.

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Citations

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